
THE ROLE OF CONCEPTUAL METAPHOR IN LITERARY TEXTS

Xalimova Firuza Rustamovna

Associate professor of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Abstract: *Many provisions of the Western theory of conceptual metaphor were known in linguistics already in the first half of the XIX century. Linguists V.G. Gak, R.B. Apresyan and N.D. Arutyunova put forward provisions on the constant reinterpretation of the original images and associations of distant concepts in the language long before J. Lakoff.*

Keywords: *linguistic metaphor, conceptual sphere, cognitive function, metaphorical expressions.*

J. Lakoff, M. Johnson and M. Turner consider metaphor to be a phenomenon of language and speech that defines a person's thought. Based on this provision, the theory of conceptual metaphor was developed. According to this theory, a metaphor is not just a language category, but a way of thinking that primarily covers a person's daily life. Thus, metaphor is placed at the center of the semantics of everyday language and makes the study of artistic metaphor a kind of extension of the theory of linguistic metaphor.

J. Lakoff introduces the term "conceptual projection", which consists in the transfer of features from one concept to another [Lakoff, 2003]. The source sphere does not necessarily have to be represented by a single conceptual sphere. Many examples involve several different concepts at once. According to cognitive scientists J. Charteris-Black, such metaphors are called "nest" [Charterise-Black, 2003].

It is considered that metaphor is an element of the analog capabilities of the human mind, one of the main mental operations, as well as a way of cognition, categorization, conceptualization, evaluation and explanation of the world [Чудинов, 2007: 54]. In addition to the cognitive function, the transformation function also stands out – the conceptual system of knowledge can change under the influence of metaphorization, which, in fact, consists either in the transformation of existing meaning, or in the formation of new meanings through the interpretation and conceptualization of new experience gained in a changing world. [Kövecses, 2015: 16]. At the same time, it is argued that conventional metaphorical expressions fill our everyday speech, and the models by which they are built are stored in long-term memory [Semino, Steen, 2008: 235].

Metaphor in the artistic language is characterized by special originality, expressiveness and complexity in terms of interpretation. This is partly due to the use of lexico-semantic deviations – linguistic elements that deviate from the norm at the level of semantics or violate the rules of semantic compatibility [Leech, 1991: 42].

A metaphor or metaphorical trope is defined as a figurative use of a sign element of a language based on assimilation. The most important characteristic of the trope is its figurative and decorative function, which is especially characteristic of metaphor, which is the most vivid expressive form of speech. When creating an image in poetry, the aesthetic function of metaphor (metaphor as a decoration of speech) and activation (metaphor as a means of activating the perception of the addressee) dominate.

Metaphor is freer than other tropes. It intersects with such figurative means as metonymy, synecdoche, hyperbole, irony, grotesque, oxymoron, epithet based on their common ability to combine many meanings. Synthesizing various expressive possibilities, metaphor declares itself as a universal means of artistic thinking, the functional potential of which is capable of the complex realization of the author's idea, to the optimal achievement of its structural and semantic integrity.

In poetry, metaphor is closely connected with hyperbole, grotesque and oxymoron, which belong to the number of figurative means of "improbable" description [Москвин 2006]. In the case of a metaphor, the degree of improbability depends on the degree of "freshness", which means the novelty of the poetic image. The literal meaning of the metaphorical name is perceived in the foyer of the nearby context as more implausible in the case of the implementation of a fresh metaphor and less implausible when the author exploits the erased metaphor.

In poetic discourse, metaphor is the most important means of forming original images that express the author's linguistic picture of the world and a poetic view of the world, which is opposed to the worldview of the inhabitant.

The effect of the poetic metaphor is due to the opposition of the ordinary vision of the world to the unusual, revealing the individual essence of the subject; the actualization of distant and non-obvious connections; the inseparability of the image and meaning; the assumption of different interpretations; the combination of boundless poetic imagination with a clear rationalistic basis; the potential for infinite combinatorial possibilities; the approximation of the distant and the elevation of the ordinary; the focus on the formation of an individual artistic image. In Uzbek tradition, the concept of an artistic image includes the author's vision of certain phenomena of the surrounding world in the context of basic universal values and abstract concepts that have the highest significance for human existence (life and death, love and hate, good and evil, etc.).

It seems that conceptual analysis is best suited for the study of metaphor as the main trope of a poetic text. In it, the concept is defined as an idiostyle construct, as a basic component of the entire poetic structure [Кузьмина 2004]. This is manifested in the fact that in a poetic text, the conceptual meaning acts as a basis, potentially containing variants of the associative deployment of meaning. The main purpose of using a metaphorical concept in a poetic text is to express an infinite variety of shades of meaning, semantic nuances, and individual perceptions. The conceptual metaphor acts as a tool of speech influence on the reader (listener), aimed at making clarifications and modifications to his model of the world by involving him in the poetic picture of the artist's world, its perception and interpretation.

List of references:

1. Charterise-Black, J. Speaking with forked tongue: A comparative study of metaphor and metonymy in English and Malay phraseology //Metaphor and Symbol, 18-4, – UK: Routledge, 2003. – 310 p.
2. Kövecses Z. Where Metaphors Come From: Reconsidering Context in Metaphor. – Oxford University Press, 2015. – 215 p.
3. Lakoff G. Metaphors We Live By. – Chicago, 2003.
4. Leech G.M. A Linguistic Guide to English Poetry. – New York: Longman Inc., 1991. – 227 p.
5. Semino E., Steen G. Metaphor in Literature // The Cambridge Handbook of Metaphor and Thought / ed. by R. W. Gibbs. – Cambridge University Press, 2008. – P. 232–247.

6. Москвин В.П. Русская метафора. Очерк семиотической теории. – М., 2006.
7. Чудинов А. П., Будаев Э. В. Когнитивная теория метафоры на современном этапе развития // Вопросы когнитивной лингвистики. 2007. № 4 (013). – С. 54–56.
8. Sherzodovich, A. S., & Jamshedovich, B. F. THE MAIN FEATURES OF THE TRANSLATION OF LITERARY TEXT. *Sciencepublish. org*, 16.
9. Халимова, Ф. Р. (2019). Прагматические свойства лингвфонетических средств в поэтическом тексте и их сравнительный анализ при переводе. *Вестник Челябинского государственного университета*, (1 (423)), 138-144.
10. Халимова, Ф. Р. (2021). КОГНИТИВ ПОЭТИКА. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 133-142.
11. RUSTAMOVNA, H. F. (2020). Training Simultaneous Interpreters. *JournalNX*, 6(06), 623-627.
12. Rustamovna, H. F. (2020). KEY CONCEPTS OF SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION. *В научный сборник вошли научные работы, посвященные широкому кругу современных проблем науки и образования, вопросов образовательных технологий 2020.*-436 с., 232.
13. Халимова, Ф. (2020). Синхрон таржима тушунчасининг асосий хусусиятлари. *Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование*, (1 (74)), 29-32.
14. Халимова, Ф. (2017). Поэтик таржимада эквивалентлик ва адекватлик тушунчаси. *Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование*, 2(2 (63)), 18-21.
15. Халимова, Ф. (2016). Эндрю моббснинг “ғазал. Таҳлил ва шаклнинг акс этиши” номли мақоласига доир мулоҳазалар. *Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование*, 1(2 (59)), 85-88.
16. Халимова, Ф. Р. (2016). AN UZBEK NATIONAL POETIC GENRE-" GAZEL" AND ITS TRANSLATION INTO UZBEK (THE EXTRACT FROM" FIROQNOMA"(A VERSE ABOUT SEPARATION), WRITTEN BY NODIRA). *Ученый XXI века*, (4-1 (17)), 57-59.